

Role of Subjective Happiness, Psychological Well-Being, Spirituality and Satisfaction with Life in Adult Psychopaths

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Abstract:- This study examined the role of Psychological Well-being, Spirituality, Subjective happiness, and satisfaction with life on the Psychopathic traits of an individual. The objective of the study was to compare the role of psychopathic traits, Psychological Well-being, Spirituality, Subjective happiness, and Satisfaction with life in individuals who have been sentenced to imprisonment (criminals). The importance of this study is, to find out whether the lack of Psychological Well-being, Subjective Happiness, Spirituality, and Satisfaction with life can predict Psychopathic traits. The recent findings show that there is a negative correlation between Psychological Well-being, Subjective Happiness, Spirituality, and Satisfaction with life and Psychopathic traits. This study was conducted using data collected from 101 prisoners from the central jail in Uttarakhand with ages ranging from 20 to 40 years. After reviewing the institutional background, a purposive sampling method was used to select the sample from the population and a cross-sectional survey research method was conducted on a closed-ended questionnaire and the response is taken on a Likert scale. Theoretical and practical implications of the results show that there is a weak negative correlation between Psychopathic traits with Spiritual Experience, Satisfaction with Life, and Subjective Happiness, and a strong positive correlation with Psychological Well Being. And Psychological Well Being is the significant predictor variable of Psychopathic traits as Dependent Variable.

Keywords:- Psychopathic traits, Psychological Well-being, Satisfaction with life, Spirituality, Subjective Happiness.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. General

The objective of current study is to find the relationship between Psychopathic traits, Psychological Well-being, Subjective Happiness, Spirituality, and Satisfaction with life, and find the role of Happiness, well-being, Spirituality, and satisfaction with life in Prisoners. This study becomes important to see whether Psychological Well-being, Subjective Happiness, Spirituality, and Satisfaction with life can predict criminal behavior or Psychopathic traits.

B. Psychopaths

The people who demonstrate psychopathy are known as Psychopaths. The condition of psychopathy considers certain specific behaviors and psychological symptoms. On the other hand, the measures of antisocial personality disorder focus mostly on behaviors visible. Psychopathy (renamed from antisocial personality disorder) is symbolized by persistent violations of social norms, deception, stealing, truancy, traffic arrests, and inconsistent work behavior.(Bhandari, 2021).

C. Antisocial personality disorder

Antisocial personality disorder (ASPD) also sometimes called sociopathy, is a mental disorder under which an individual doesn't show any regard for right and wrong and ignores the rights and feelings of others. Individuals with antisocial personality disorder have total disregard for other people who claim to irritate, control, or treat others brutally or with a hard lack of concern. They don't show any guilt or remorse for their behavior. (Bhandari, 2021)

People with an antisocial personality disorder often violate the law and become criminals. They can lie, impulsively, behave violently, and have problems with drug and alcohol abuse. Because of these characteristics, individuals suffering from this disorder have difficulty fulfilling responsibilities related to family, work, or school. (Bhandari, 2021)

D. Psychological well-being

Psychological well-being explains an individual's emotional health and overall functioning. The author of 'Health and Well-Being' published in 'Applied Psychology' describes psychological well-being as "the combination of feeling good and functioning effectively.

There are typically 2 types of psychological well-being which are hedonics and eudemonics. The term "Hedonic" well-being is normally referred to as the subjective feelings of happiness. It additionally contains two segments, a full-of-feeling segment (high good effect and lowregrettable effect) and a psychological part (fulfillment with life). It is proposed that a person experiences happiness when positive affect and satisfaction with life are both high. The less notable term, "Eudaimonic" prosperity is utilized to allude to the

deliberate part of PWB. The psychologist Carol Ryff has built up an unmistakable model that separates Eudaimonic prosperity into six key kinds of mental prosperity which are Self-acceptance (which shows the respondent's positive attitude about his or herself), Environmental mastery(which includes managing everyday affairs and creating situations to benefit personal needs), Positive relationships(which involves reciprocal empathy, intimacy, and affection), Personal growth(which consists of welcoming to new experiences and recognizes improvement in behavior and self over time), Purpose in life(involves strong goal orientation and conviction that life holds meaning), and Autonomy(which means independence from social pressures).(Robertson, 2021).

E. Satisfaction with life

It refers to our common feeling about our life and how conscious we are of how it's going. An ample of factors contribute to life satisfaction, including work, romantic relationships, relationships with family and friends, personal development, health and wellness, and others. Higher levels of life satisfaction are associated with good overall physical health and fewer long-term health conditions (Siahpush, Spittal, & Singh, 2008). Happiness and life satisfaction tentatively foresee self-evaluated well-being, actual well-being, and the presence of restricting long-haul medical issues.(Siahpush, Spittal & Singh, 2008)

F. Spirituality

Spirituality refers to an individual's recognition of a feeling or sense or belief that there is something greater than self, something more to being human than sensory experience and that the more noteworthy entire of which we are part is grandiose or divine. It also means, knowing that our lives have significance in a context beyond everyday existence at the level of biological needs that drive greediness, selfishness, and aggression. This means, knowing that we are a significant part of a purposeful unfolding of life in the universe. Spirituality comprises investigating certain all-inclusive topics like – love, empathy, philanthropy, post-existence, shrewdness, and truth, with the feeling that a few groups like holy people or illuminated people have accomplished and shown more significant levels of improvement than the customary populace.(Spencer, 2021)

G. Subjective happiness

Subjective happiness refers to a subjective experience that has special significance for humans. A few antiquated and present-day researchers, including Aristotle and Bentham, contended that happiness was a definitive objective of life. Empirical psychological studies of subjective happiness have shown that the construct can be measured reliably over time, is strongly influenced by genetic factors, and consists of emotional (e.g., experiencing more joy and less disappointment) and intellectual (e.g., assessing one's life as great) parts.Psychological studies have shown that happiness can be estimated dependably and comprises emotional and cognitive components.(Sato et al., 2015)

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Psychopathy is a character build portrayed by shallow effect, absence of sympathy, and hastiness. Love and Holder examined the relations between psychopathy, abstract prosperity, and character in 427 students. Pervasiveness rates for psychopathy, given members who embraced at least eight essential psychopathy things, were 22.6% of guys and 7.5% of females. The study found that psychopathy was associated with immensely high levels of depression and immensely negative affect, and very low levels of life satisfaction, happiness, and positive affect.Psychopathy represented significant parts of the change in discouragement (16.6%), negative effect (16.9%), life fulfillment (13.7%), satisfaction (14.4–18.3%), and positive effect (9.8%). Nonetheless, it is also seen that psychopathy neglected to represent a change in either a sick being or prosperity far over the fluctuation represented by a character. These outcomes support the position that psychopathy can be considered a heavenly body of outrageous degrees of regularizing character attributes. (Love and Holder, 2014)

According to the study byAli and Chamorro-Premuzic, the degree to which primary psychopathy, secondary psychopathy, Machiavellianism, gender, sociosexual orientation, and the related components of intimacy, commitment, and passion, accounted for variance in life satisfaction. The result shows that Machiavellianism was negatively associated with the related components. Surprisingly, primary psychopathy was positively connected with the connected segments. Secondary psychopathy was negatively connected with life satisfaction and intimacy. (Ali and Chamorro-Premuzic, 2010)

Lata & Chaudhary found a negative correlation between workplace spirituality and incivility experienced by the two sources (supervisors and colleagues). On the other side, the only psychopathy moderated the connection between workplace spirituality and supervisor incivility in Sample 1, the moderation effect of all three dark triads was significant in the case of colleague incivility. Sample 2 shows, that each member of the dark triad shows the association between workplace spirituality and incivility experienced by seniors and peers. The outcomes offered help for the cognitive appraisal theory by clarifying how the act of working environment spirituality adjusts representatives' impression of uncivil practices appeared by their bosses and friends. (Lata & Chaudhary, 2020)

Ongoing discoveries in Durand's investigation have given proof of a negative relationship between psychopathy and happiness.To decide whether this relationship is generalizable to all subtypes of psychopathy, members from the local area (N = 572) were selected to look at happiness-related highlights among guys and females. Assessment of the Fearless-Dominance (PPI-I) and Impulsive-Antisociality (PPI-II) subscales of the Psychopathic Personality Inventory-Short Form gave proof to two unmistakable examples when contrasting psychopathic character qualities with satisfaction-related

highlights. PPI-I was positively associated with higher sturdy happiness, presence of importance throughout everyday life, self-improvement, and trust, and corresponded adversely with fluctuating happiness. PPI-II was negatively correlated with durable happiness, presence of meaning in life, personal growth, and hope, and correlated positively with fluctuating happiness and searching for meaning in life. Despite a couple of contrasts, the two sexual orientations showed a comparable example between proportions of well-being and psychopathic subtypes. Suggestions for psychopathy concerning the significance of performing investigations by sex and subtypes are examined. (Durand, 2016)

As indicated by Arbuckle and Cunningham, Psychopathy can be considered as a measurement moored toward one side by an absence of worry for other people. Indeed, even in its milder structures, psychopathy can prompt ordinary standoffish conduct, like cheating, misdirecting, or getting into fistfights. Although a lack of concern for others is the point of focus of the concept of psychopathy, it is not clear whether this stems from differences in ability or motivation. (Arbuckle & Cunningham, 2012)

Polaschek & Daly review past and recent research on psychopathy and treatment, concluding that a handful of newer, well-designed studies suggest grounds for optimism about psychopathy and treatability. Although psychopathy characteristics—along with other indices of criminal risk—signal responsivity challenges, well-conceived programs for higher-risk offenders can decrease recidivism in highly psychopathic offenders and appear to do so by reducing dynamic risk factors. There are still no clear shreds of evidence of whether PCL-psychopathic perpetrators differ from other high-risk perpetrators in their ability to respond to such treatments. (Polaschek & Daly, 2013)

Psychological well-being refers to inter-individual and intra-individual levels of positive functioning that can consist of one's relatedness to others. Burns says that Subjective well-being reflects criteria of judgments of life satisfaction. The idea of well-being has gotten extensive interest in a couple of past years, both in logical and lay writing. As such, well-being is more often cited as a national priority for policymaking in government agencies around the world. (Burns, 2016)

Subjective happiness has two effective constituents. One is called, a full-of-feeling constituent which alludes to 'hedonic levels' (how much the different impacts singular encounters are charming), Second, (the cognitive constituent) is called 'contentment' (how much an individual sees his yearning to be met). These two dimensions of happiness, define happiness in two parts: psychological happiness focusing on the state of mind, and prudential happiness focusing on well-being. Surely, happiness relies upon both psychological and passionate parts. In this respect, Sariçam says that it could be argued that happiness presents the individual. Conclusively, subjective happiness is an essential factor for social happiness or life satisfaction. (Sariçam, 2015)

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Tools Used

a) Psychological well Being

Carol Ryff has interpreted psychological well-being with 6 dimensions: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. She designed self-report scales to assess a person's well-being at a particular moment in time within each of these 6 dimensions consisting of 3 to 12 items per scale. Responses to various statements are taken on a 6-point Likert scale. A greater score on every scale indicates higher well-being in that dimension. (Ryff, 2020)

b) Subjective happiness scale

The SHS is a 4-item scale with two things request that respondents describe themselves utilizing both outright appraisals and evaluations compared with peers, though the other two things offer brief depictions of glad and troubled people. Furthermore, ask respondents the degree to which every portrayal depicts them. The SHS has been accredited in 14 examinations with a sum of 2,732 members. Results have demonstrated that the SHS has high internal consistency, which is steady across tests. Test-retest and self-peer correlations have recommended great to fantastic unwavering quality and build approval investigations of merged and discriminant legitimacy have affirmed the utilization of this scale to gauge the construct of subjective happiness. (Lyubomirsky, 2020)

c) Satisfaction with life scale

The Satisfaction with life scale consists of 5 items and 7-point rating scale. The scale has been demonstrated to be a legitimate and solid proportion of life fulfillment, showing high internal consistency and unwavering quality and appropriate for use with various age gatherings and populations (DIENER, 2020)

d) Triarchic Psychopathy Measure (TriPM)

The essence of the Triarchic model is that psychopathy encompasses three distinct phenotypic constructs: disinhibition, boldness, and meanness. The Triarchic conceptualization gives a premise to accommodating constantly elective engaging records of psychopathy, and a structure for organizing research on neurobiological and formative cycles adding to changing manifestations of the disorder. The scale consists of 58 items with 4 alternative options to choose from. (Patrick, Fowles & Krueger, 2009)

e) Spiritual Experience Index-Revised (SEI-R)

A 23-item scale that actions faith and spiritual excursion, meaning to not force specific confidence as a feature of the inquiries. This poll is an updated rendition of the Spiritual Experience Index. For the most part, the first has been abbreviated, and,

through factor examination, been changed into two subscales: Spiritual Support (13 inquiries) and Spiritual Openness (10 inquiries). (Genia, 1997)

- A cross-sectional survey research method was used for Research Design.
- The data was collected on a (non-comparative) interval scale.

B. Research Design

- After the study of the background/institutional history of the offender and reports of basic health check-ups, the purposive sampling method was used to select a sample from a population of central prisons.
- Whereas 101 prisoners were chosen from Central (Open) Jail in Sitarganj Udham Singh Nagar District Uttarakhand.
- A survey research method was used for data collection of ages ranging from 20 to 40 years and was comprised of a questionnaire of closed-ended questions (as mentioned above) and responses were taken on the Likert Scale.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics show that 66.3% of convicted people are from urban areas. It is also evident from the frequency distribution that 40.6% of prisoners were from lower middle-class families whereas 41.6% have an extended type of family. 81.2% of people were not a single child of their parents. It was found that 36% of the prisoners did only primary-level education. The mean score of the Subjective Happiness Scale, Psychological well-being, Satisfaction with life, Psychopathy, and Spirituality is 10.45, 156.25, 12.51, 64.81, and 58.33 respectively.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
SHS Total	101	4	27	10.45	5.852
PWBS Total	101	42	180	156.25	28.308
SLS Total	101	5	32	12.51	5.810
TRIPM Total	100	0	103	64.81	25.136
SEI Total	101	23	109	58.33	17.370
Valid N (listwise)	100				

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Whereas the descriptive statistics in Table 1 show that the Standard Deviation of Psychopathic traits, Subjective Happiness, Satisfaction with Life, Psychological Well Being, and Spiritual Experience are 22.455, 7.080, 8.680, 35.665, and 21.324 respectively meanwhile the mean score are 70.69, 15.09, 18.34, 177.02, and 72.03 respectively.

B. Correlation

In addition, the results of the correlation analysis in Table 2 showed that there is a positive correlation between all the variables. The Correlation was significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The Pearson correlation shows that there is a significant strong positive correlation between Subjective Happiness with Satisfaction with Life, Spiritual Experience with $r = +0.77$ and $+0.79$ respectively, and a non-significant weak negative correlation with Psychological Well Being with $r = -0.003$ and a significant weak negative correlation with Psychopathic trait with a score of $r = -0.254$. Whereas Satisfaction with life significantly shows a strong positive correlation with Spiritual Experience with a score of $r =$

$+0.624$ and a non-significant weak correlation with psychological well-being with $r = +0.03$ whereas satisfaction with life shows a non-significant weak negative correlation with Psychopathic trait with $r = -0.005$ respectively. Psychological Well-Being was found to be significantly strongly positively correlated with Psychopathic traits with $r = +0.503$ and weak and positively correlated with Spiritual Experience with a score of $r = +0.314$ respectively. And then it was evident that the Psychopathic trait was non significantly showing a weakly negative correlation with Spiritual Experience with a score of $r = -0.111$. The Pearson correlation was tested on a two-tailed test with a significance level of 0.01 (99% level of significance). It was also seen that Subjective happiness has a strong positive correlation between Satisfaction with life and Spiritual experience whereas Satisfaction with life and spiritual experience are strongly positively correlated with each other. Psychological well-being is strongly positively correlated with Psychopathy and Spirituality.

		SHS Total	SLS Total	PWBS Total	TRIPM Total	SEI Total
SHS Total	Pearson Correlation	1	.770**	-.003	-.254*	.796**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.973	.010	.000
	N	101	101	101	101	101
SLS Total	Pearson Correlation	.770**	1	.033	-.005	.624**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.740	.964	.000
	N	101	101	101	101	101
PWBS Total	Pearson Correlation	-.003	.033	1	.503**	.314**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.973	.740		.000	.001
	N	101	101	101	101	101
TRIPM Total	Pearson Correlation	-.254*	-.005	.503**	1	-.111
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	.964	.000		.269
	N	101	101	101	101	101
SEI Total	Pearson Correlation	.796**	.624**	.314**	-.111	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.001	.269	
	N	101	101	101	101	101

Table 2: Correlations

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

C. Regression

Logistic Regression analysis in Table 3 shows that R, R square, and Adjusted R square are 0.639, 0.408, and 0.383 respectively, which indicates a good level of prediction and a very good regression analysis. The Table 4 also shows the overall regression model is a good fit for the data with an F ratio of 16.530 which is significant at a 0.05 level of significance. This also shows that the independent variables (Subjective Happiness, Satisfaction with Life, and psychological well-being) significantly predict the dependent variable (Psychopathy). It is also evident in Table

6 that Psychological Well Being, Subjective happiness, and satisfaction with life is the significant predictor variable of Psychopathic trait in adults with t =6.153, -2.179, and 3.456 respectively which is significant at a 0.05 level of significance. The nonstandard coefficient in Table 5 shows how much a dependent variable varies with the independent variable and here it is seen that psychological well-being, Subjective Happiness, and Satisfaction with Life vary with psychopathy by 0.485, -1.558, and 1.774 respectively. The Standardized Coefficients value (Beta Value) is 0.568, -0.377, and 0.426 respectively.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.639 ^a	.408	.383	18.998

Table 3: Model Summary

a. Predictors: (Constant), SEI Total, PWBS Total, SLS Total, SHS Total

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23864.552	4	5966.138	16.530	.000 ^b
	Residual	34649.686	96	360.934		
	Total	58514.238	100			

Table 4: ANOVA

a. Dependent Variable: TRIPM Total

b. Predictors: (Constant), SEI Total, PWBS Total, SLS Total, SHS Total

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	4.272	11.347		.377	.707	-18.251	26.796
SHS Total	-1.558	.715	-.377	-2.179	.032	-2.978	-.139
SLS Total	1.774	.513	.426	3.456	.001	.755	2.793
PWBS Total	.485	.079	.568	6.153	.000	.329	.642
SEI Total	-.355	.212	-.255	-1.674	.097	-.776	.066

Table 5: Coefficients

a. Dependent Variable: TRIPM Total

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	13.26	87.52	65.28	15.448	101
Residual	-50.522	32.061	.000	18.614	101
Std. Predicted Value	-3.367	1.440	.000	1.000	101
Std. Residual	-2.659	1.688	.000	.980	101

Table 6: Residuals Statistics

a. Dependent Variable: TRIPM Total

V. DISCUSSION

The results show that there is a statistical difference in the mean score of satisfaction with life and Spiritual Experience. It was also evident that there is no statistical difference in the mean score of Psychological Well-Being, Psychopathic trait, and Subjective Happiness. The results of this study also match the literature and basic overview of the previous studies mentioned in the literature review.

In addition, the results of the correlation analysis showed that there is a correlation between all the variables with either positive or negative which matches with a few of the studies' literature reviews. The Correlation was significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The Pearson correlation shows that there is a significantly weak negative relationship between Psychopathic traits with Spiritual Experience, Satisfaction with Life, and Subjective Happiness and a strong positive correlation with Psychological Well Being. It was also seen that Subjective happiness has a strong positive correlation between Satisfaction with life and Spiritual experience whereas Satisfaction with life and spiritual experience are strongly positively correlated with each other. Psychological well-being is strongly positively correlated with Psychopathy and Spirituality. The results indicate that there is a significantly weak negative relationship between Psychopathic traits with Spiritual Experience, Satisfaction with Life, and Subjective Happiness, and a strong positive correlation with Psychological Well Being.

Logistic Regression analysis shows that Psychological Well Being, Subjective happiness, and satisfaction with life is the significant predictor variable of Psychopathic trait in adults with t =6.153, -2.179, and 3.456 respectively which is significant at a 0.05 level of significance whereas Psychological Well-being, Subjective Happiness, and

Satisfaction with Life varies with psychopathy by 0.485, -1.558 and 1.774 respectively.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study examined the role of Psychological Well-being, Spirituality, Subjective happiness, and satisfaction with life on the Psychopathic traits of an individual using a sample from prison. After looking into the results, we can conclude that there is a statistical difference in the mean score of satisfaction with life and Spiritual Experience with other variables of prisoners. It was also evident that there is a statistical difference in the mean score of Psychological Well-Being, Psychopathic trait, and Subjective Happiness. The correlation analysis showed that there is a significant weak negative relationship between Psychopathic traits with Spiritual Experience, Satisfaction with Life, and Subjective Happiness and a strong positive correlation with Psychological Well Being which matches with the results of Love and Holder, Ali and Chamorro-Premuzic, Durand, Park and other studies in the literature review section. It was also seen that Subjective happiness has a strong positive correlation between Satisfaction with life and Spiritual experience whereas Satisfaction with life and spiritual experience are strongly positively correlated with each other. Psychological well-being is strongly positively correlated with Psychopathy and Spirituality. Whereas the increase in the level of Psychopathic traits can have an increase in Psychological Well-being and satisfaction with life and vice-versa. Whereas the increased level of psychopathic traits can have decreased Subjective happiness and spirituality. There is a similarity found between Satisfaction with life and Spiritual Experience. Whereas, Psychological well-being can conclude to criminal behavior or psychopathy, or can say that an increased level of psychopathy can conclude to psychological well-being and vice-versa. We can also conclude that a high level of

psychological well-being can be seen in Psychopathic prisoners. We can also expect that psychopathic offenders can be identified by their increased level of psychological well-being and low level of life satisfaction. Furthermore, studies can be done in the future on the same issue by taking a larger sample and doing a comparative study with different populations. Or else can have a comparative study between different kinds of prisons and can be geographically determinant. The understanding of antisocial personality disorder and psychopathic behavioral traits can allow authorities to design strategies that will more likely work with prisoners. This study on Psychopathy is an early warning sign of severe and persistent violence. Psychopathy-related violence accounts for a considerable share of the societal burden on the public health and criminal justice systems, necessitating significant attention from preventive specialists.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

The first recommendation states the sample size. A small sample size of 101 prisoners was chosen whereas one can have a similar kind of study on a larger sample size. The second recommendation is that one can correlate the different prisons (district, sub-jail, Central., etc.) in a different state, as the state plays a vital role in spirituality because the Uttarakhand is known as the 'Land of God' and the prisoners involved in this study were mostly from the Uttarakhand domicile which could be the cause of the high level of spirituality in them. The third recommendations concern that before collecting data an institutional review was conducted and then the sample was chosen where most of the prisoners have completed at least 5 years of imprisonment and therefore a study could be conducted on the prisoner within a tenure of an initial 1 year of imprisonment for the sake of any kind of remorse and can be correlated with the present study to see the differences in the first-time offenders and psychopaths.

ABBREVIATIONS

SHS – Subjective happiness scale, SLS – Satisfaction with life, PWBS – Psychological well-being, TRIPM – Triarchic psychopathic measure, SEI – Spiritual experience index.

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